

Analyzing Student Gaming Behavior and Academic Responsibility Using a Rule-Based Algorithm

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Abstract- Online gaming is prevalent among college students and has the potential to influence the management of academic responsibilities. This study investigates student gaming behaviour through the application of a rule-based classification algorithm. Data were obtained from 30 participants using a structured questionnaire addressing gaming frequency, duration, time of play, study time allocation, and task completion rate. Findings reveal that most students exhibit balanced gaming behaviour, indicating that responsible gaming does not inherently impact academic performance.

Keywords- online gaming, academic responsibility, rule-based classification algorithm, behavioural analysis, student gaming behaviour

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1. Introduction

Online gaming has become common among college students and is part of their daily lives. Students play games for fun, to connect with others, and to relieve stress. Some manage to balance gaming with their studies, but others struggle with time management, which can hurt their study habits, grades, and sleep. Previous research has looked at how online gaming affects academic performance. Too much gaming is linked to lower concentration, poorer grades, and weak time management [1], [2], [4]. On the other hand, moderate gaming does not necessarily harm academic results and can help reduce stress and keep students mentally engaged when done responsibly [3], [5]. Gaming habits can

also affect how students think and feel, depending on how they play [6]. Even with these findings, most research focuses on total gaming hours or general screen time. Few studies look closely at specific gaming habits, like how often students play, how long each session lasts, or what time of day they play, and how these relate to managing schoolwork. Many studies also use only basic descriptions and do not have a clear way to classify different gaming behaviors.

To fill this gap, this study presents a rule-based scoring system to see how college students balance online gaming with their schoolwork. The system looks at different gaming habits and sorts students into three groups: balanced, stress-relief, and risky gaming behaviors.

2. Framework

2.1 Conceptual Framework

This study uses a behavioural analysis framework to look at how students' gaming habits relate to how they handle their academic responsibilities. The framework combines survey data with a rule-based classification algorithm to find patterns in college students' gaming activities.

The conceptual framework uses an Input-Process-Output (IPO) model to organize and analyze the data. In this model, the input is made up of measurable signs of gaming and academic responsibility, collected through a survey. These inputs are processed with a rule-based scoring algorithm built in

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Python. The algorithm reviews the behavioural data and gives each respondent a total score based on set scoring rules. The input variables include gaming frequency, gaming duration, time of play, study time, and task completion rate. These factors show students’ gaming habits and how they handle their academic work. Each variable is scored according to the respondent’s answers. The algorithm totals these scores and uses specific thresholds to determine the respondent’s gaming behaviour category. The system then places student gaming behaviour into three groups: Balanced Gaming Behaviour, Stress-Relief Gaming Behaviour, and Risky Gaming Behaviour. These categories help explain how students balance gaming with their studies.

2.2 Methodology Framework

This methodological framework describes how we analyzed gaming behaviour among college students. It explains the steps for collecting, processing, and analyzing data with a rule-based classification algorithm.

The process starts by collecting survey data through Google Forms. College students answer questions about their gaming habits and academic responsibilities.

Their responses are exported to a CSV file, which is used as the input dataset for analysis. The dataset is processed with a Python-based classification algorithm. Each survey response is scored using set rules. The algorithm calculates a total behavioural score for each student based on gaming frequency, gaming duration, time of play, study time, and task completion rate. After the scores are calculated, the system sorts students into three groups: Balanced Gaming Behaviour, Stress-Relief Gaming Behaviour, and Risky Gaming Behaviour. In the final step, the process produces a CSV file with the results, summary statistics, and a chart showing the distribution.

Figure 2. Algorithm processing flow of the Study

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study uses a descriptive-analytical quantitative research design to explore how college students balance online gaming with their academic work. It looks at patterns in gaming frequency, gaming duration, time of play, study time, and how students complete academic tasks.

Instead of only using descriptive statistics like many traditional studies, this research also uses an algorithm-based classification method. Survey data are analyzed with a rule-based scoring algorithm written in Python. This allows for automated and objective analysis of students' behavior patterns.

3.2 Research Participants

The study involved 30 college students who regularly play online games. Participants were chosen through convenience sampling, with a focus on students who often play online games to make sure the behavioural data collected was relevant.

Taking part in the survey was voluntary, and participants were told their information would only be used for academic research. Email addresses were collected just to avoid duplicate responses and keep the data accurate, while still protecting participants' confidentiality

3.3 Data Collection Instrument

A structured online questionnaire was used to collect behavioral data from participants. The survey, distributed through Google Forms, asked about gaming habits and how students handle their academic responsibilities.

The questionnaire looked at five main variables:

- Gaming frequency (days per week)
- Gaming duration (hours per day)
- Time of play
- Study time allocation (hours per day)
- Task completion rate (percentage of academic tasks completed on time)

3.4 Algorithm Design

We developed a rule-based scoring algorithm to assess how students balance gaming with their academic responsibilities.

Each behavioural factor is given a score from 1 to 3, based on the student's reported habits. Lower scores show more balanced behaviour, while higher scores suggest a greater risk.

The algorithm adds up the scores from all five factors to get a total behavioural score.

Total Score = Frequency + Duration + Time of Play + Study Time + Task Completion

Based on the total score, the algorithm places each student into one of these categories:

- Balanced Gaming Behaviour (5–8 points)
- Stress-Relief Gaming Behaviour (9–12 points)
- Risky Gaming Behaviour (13–15 points)

We implemented the algorithm in Python. The system reads survey responses from CSV files, calculates behavioural scores, classifies students, and creates summary reports and visualizations automatically.

3.5 Data Analysis

Survey data were exported from Google Forms in CSV format and processed using a Python-based classification system. The program automatically calculates behavioural scores for each respondent and assigns them to predefined gaming behaviour categories. Descriptive statistical techniques, including frequency distribution and percentage analysis, were applied to summarize the results. These methods present the number of respondents in each gaming behaviour category.

The system also generates graphical visualizations using the Matplotlib library in Python to illustrate the distribution of classification results among respondents.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Classification Results of Student Gaming Behaviour

The survey gathered answers from 30 college students who regularly play online games. The data were exported from Google Forms as a CSV file and analyzed with a rule-based classification algorithm in Python. This algorithm looked at five factors: how often and how long students played, when they played, how much time they spent studying, and how often they finished academic tasks. After analyzing the survey data, the students were sorted into three groups based on their gaming habits: Balanced Gaming Behaviour, Stress-Relief Gaming Behaviour, and Risky Gaming Behaviour.

Table 1 shows that most students, 23 out of 30 (76.67%), were in the Balanced Gaming Behaviour group. Seven students (23.33%) were in the Stress-Relief Gaming Behaviour group, meaning they mainly play games to relax and it does not affect their studies much.

No Students were placed in the Risky Gaming Behaviour group, which suggests that this group of students generally plays games responsibly.

The visual data also shows that most students are in the balanced gaming group. This suggests that, in this sample, college students are usually able to balance gaming with their schoolwork.

Behavior Category	Number of Students	Percentage
Balanced Gaming Behavior	23	76.67%
Stress-Relief Gaming Behavior	7	23.33%
Risky Gaming Behavior	0	0%
Total	30	100%

Table 1. Present the distribution of respondents across of the three classification categories

Figure 3. Distribution of Student Gaming Behavior Classification

4.2 Discussion

The results show that online gaming does not always cause poor academic outcomes if students play responsibly. Many students in the study managed to balance gaming with their studies without hurting their academic performance. Some students use gaming to cope with academic stress. This matches earlier research showing that gaming can help people relax when done the limited sample size. Future research involving larger populations may provide a broader understanding of gaming behavior.

5. Conclusion

This study looked at how college students manage online gaming along with their academic work. Researchers used a survey and a rule-based scoring system in Python to measure things like how often students play games, how long they play, when they play, how much time they spend studying, and whether they finish their academic tasks.

Out of 30 college students from various programs, most showed balanced gaming habits. About 77% were considered balanced gamers, meaning they could play games responsibly and still keep up with their studies. Around 23% used gaming mainly to relax or manage stress. None of the students showed risky gaming behaviour.

These results suggest that moderate gaming does not get in the way of students' academic work. Many college students are able to balance gaming with their studies.

Using the rule-based scoring system also shows that algorithms can help analyze behaviour data. Automating the process gives a clear and objective way to look at students' gaming habits.

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